

A Study on Socio Economic Prominence of Consumer Behaviour of Buying Dairy Products: With Special Reference to Arokya Milk in Coimbatore City

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Abstract

This study has been analyses on socio economic prominence of consumer behaviour of buying dairy products: with special reference to arokya milk in Coimbatore city. India is 'The Oyster' of the global dairy industry. It offers opportunities to entrepreneurs worldwide, who wish to capitalize on one of the world's largest and fastest growing markets for milk and milk products. A bagful of 'pearls' awaits the international dairy processor in India. The Indian dairy industry is rapidly growing, trying to keep pace with the galloping progress around the world. As he expands his overseas operations to India many profitable options await him. He may transfer technology, sign joint ventures or use India as a sourcing centre for regional exports. The liberalization of the Indian economy beckons to MNC's and foreign investors alike. Keeping in view potential and trends, it is important that we find new wage and means and technologies for processing into different dairy products," Singh said. He also said that he strongly believes our institutions of agricultural research and education will attain the highest levels of excellence in development of technologies and competent human resources to effectively deal with new challenges in the changing scenario.

Keywords: Technology, Dairy Products, Indian Economy and MNC's

Introduction of the Study

From this learn have been determined India is 'The Oyster' of the global dairy industry. It offers opportunities to entrepreneurs worldwide, who wish to capitalize on one of the world's largest and fastest growing markets for milk and milk products. A bagful of 'pearls' awaits the international dairy processor in India. The Indian dairy industry is

rapidly growing, trying to keep pace with the galloping progress around the world. As he expands his overseas operations to India many profitable options await him. He may transfer technology, sign joint ventures or use India as a sourcing centre for regional exports. The liberalization of the Indian economy beckons to MNC's and foreign investors alike.

India's dairy sector is expected to triple its production in the next 10 years in view of expanding potential for export to Europe and the West. Moreover with WTO regulations expected to come into force in coming years all the developed countries which are among big exporters today would have to withdraw the support and subsidy to their domestic milk products sector. Also India today is the lowest cost producer of per litre of milk in the world, at 27 cents, compared with the U.S' 63 cents, and Japan's \$2.8 dollars. R. G. Chandramogan is the chairman and managing director of Hatsun Agro Product Ltd, which is the manufacturer of branded milk and ice cream and the largest private dairy in India. Arun Ice Creams, a popular ice cream brand in south India is owned by Hatsun Agro. Hatsun group is also producing Arokya and Gomatha, two popular milk brands in Tamil Nadu. The company is expected to cross 3000 crore rupees turnover in year 2009. He is one of the first generation of entrepreneurs from Sivakasi. He is one among the 41 Indian Billionaires.

"The net returns on investment range from 15-30 per cent on commercial dairy herds in dynamic milk regions, while profit margins on small-holder farms are below 10 per cent in several regions. This would help in attracting the rural youths in adapting dairying as a profession," he said. He also pointed out that the consumption of milk and its products has increased in both rural and urban food baskets.

"In the past decades, there has been an increase in the consumption of milk and milk products in rural and urban areas by 29 and 26 per cent, respectively. "The consumer preferences in India are diversifying towards high value added dairy products such as dairy beverages, fermented milk products, Western dairy products, functional dairy products, and packaged traditional dairy products. "Market growth rate for some of these products is in the range of 15-20 per cent and also Coimbatore has fastest growing corporation in all over the tamilnadu.

Keeping in view possibilities and trends, it is important that we find new wage and means and technologies for processing into different dairy products," Singh said. He also said that he strongly believes our institutions of agricultural research and education will attain the highest levels of excellence in development of technologies and competent human resources to effectively deal with new challenges in the changing scenario. The above said information its very necessary analyses to find out the dairy products usage in Coimbatore and selected convincing samples.

"Arokya Milk is full of the Natural Richness of Our Villages and Collected with Care from Healthy, Well Fed cows, following defined guidelines "Launched in 1995, this brand is the trusted choice of millions in Tamil Nadu, Karnataka & Andhra Pradesh, making it the Largest Milk Brand from the Indian Private sector today.

Available in a variety of sizes, the brand has two product variants

- Standardized Milk
- Full Cream Milk

This gain knowledge of mainly concentrate on socio economic prominence of consumer behavior of buying dairy products: with special reference to arokya milk in Coimbatore city and also nearly 100 primary survey illustration have been helped analyze.

Scope of the Study

The aim of this study is to empirically investigate the consumer buying behaviour (purchase intention) of Arokya Milk in Coimbatore. Identify the key factors which may influence consumer's buying behavior. And thereby, the organization could able to find the way to improve the sales of Arokya milk by meeting the customer expectations.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is when, why, how, and where people do/do not buy a product. It attempts to understand the buyer decision making process, both individually and in groups.

- To find out Socio Economic eminence of Consumer Behaviour of Buying Dairy Products to Arokya Milk in Coimbatore City.
- To appreciate the satisfaction level of customers in dairy products.
- To give suggestion did brand loyalty of consumer.

Hypothesis

- There is any relationship between various quality and gender.
- There is any relationship between contentment of buying dairy products

Sources of Data

The primary survey method is followed by preparing the questionnaire and conducting the direct interview. A secondary source of data is also collected for the reference.

Sample Size

The sample size has been conveniently selected 100 respondents for the study purpose only.

Sampling Technique

Sampling performance used is convenience sampling. This is a non-probability sampling technique which is dictated by the needs of expediency rather than any other considerations.

Statistical Tools Used

SPSS is used for analyzing the data

- Percentage analysis
- Descriptive analysis
- Graphical analysis

Limitation of the Study

- This study has been conducting Consumer buying behavior may differ from person to person and thereby it would be tricky to provide common idea.
- From this study to give the Information be collected from primary sources for this reason there would be chance for a biased or ambiguous response.

Review of Literature

The following supportive study has been focus on primary survey method is followed by preparing the questionnaire and conducting the direct interview. A secondary source of data is also collected for the reference. Celebrity Endorsements and its impact on Consumer Buying Behaviour– amit kumar, M.Sc Management with Marketing, (2014) It was proven in this research that consumers find celebrity endorsements more attractive and influential as compared to non-celebrity endorsements. In other terms, celebrity attributes do impact the purchase intention of consumers. Finally, the results of the study prove that celebrity endorsements positively impact the purchase intention of the consumers. Impact of Creative Advertising on the Buying Behaviour of Consumers” by Allwyn Deepak mathi as in (2009-2011). In present day advertising, creative advertisements have become more like a weapon for the advertisers to reach the minds of the target customers. We can see a number of humorous advertisements with a creative and appealing content in them. They can be in Electronic media or print media or any other medium which are assessable to the viewers. Customer Buying Behaviour Case Study”: Algol Technics, Weckman, Nina (2009). The purpose of this study is to assist the case company in concluding whether they are using the right marketing approach in a specific market. The company supplies driver seats to retailers and end users, and the sales team requested a research of the consumer behaviours and preferences in

the construction machinery market where they have the lowest market share compared to their other product markets. It is therefore important to understand the customer values and the major preferences, for instance the quality versus price, levels of services, brand loyalty, distribution channels. Consumer Buying Behaviour in India: Consumer Buying Behaviour in India (Bellman 2007) Since, India’s economic liberalization policies were introduced in 1991; Eliminated import licensing restrictions and reduced tariffs has led many foreign companies to enter the Indian market. India has always been a lucrative and large market for US brands and advertising (Bellman 2007). Today, Indian market has transformed from a seller’s market to buyer’s market. The increased consumer power has fierce the competition in the market. This has led to the price war and has forced the companies to maintain product quality to sustain in the highly competitive market like India. Consumer Buying Behaviour Lancaster et al. (2005) Consumer Buying Behaviour that satisfaction of consumer In today’s dynamic and competitive environment, customers are continuously exposed to various different brands through different marketing strategies. Consumer behaviour is an important and complex area for marketers as different people have different needs. As stated by Lancaster et al. (2005) that satisfaction of consumer needs is the ultimate goal for a business; thus the marketer’s job is to accurately identify the customer needs and accordingly develop product that satisfies their wants. As above the reviews have been helped to analyse.

Analysis and Discussion

Table 3.1.1
Age Group of the Respondents

Age Group	Total
14-25 yrs	30
26-40 yrs	37
41-55 yrs	23
56 above	10
Total	100

Source: Primary Survey 2018

Out of 100 respondents, 30 respondents were under the age group of 14-25, 37 respondents were under the age group of 26-40, 23 respondents were under 41-55 and 10 respondents were above 56.

Table 3.1.2
Respondent Occupation

Occupation	Total
Government	27
Private	38
Business	16
Other	19
Total	100

Source: Primary Survey 2018

The occupations of Out of 100 respondents, 27 respondents were Government, 38 respondents were private, 16 respondents were business and 19 respondents were other people.

Table 3.1.3
Education Qualification of the Respondents

Education Qualification	Total
Primary	10
Middle School	27
Higher School	32
Any Degree	31
Total	100

Source: Primary Survey 2018

Out of 100 respondents, 10 respondents were primary school, 27 respondents were middle school, 32 respondents were Higher School and 31 respondents were any degree.

Table 3.1.4
Respondents Income

Income	Total
1000<5000	8
5001<10000	29
10001<25000	43
25001 AND ABOVE	20
Total	100

Source: Primary Survey 2018

Out of 100 respondents, 8 respondents were 1000-5000, 29 respondents were 5001-10000, 10001-25000 respondents were 43. 25001 And Above 20 were business people.

Table 3.1.5
Consuming Dairy Brand of the Respondents

Dairy Brand	Total
Price	12
Quality	21
Service	29
Advertisement	38
Total	100

Source: Primary Survey 2018

Out of 100 respondents, 12 respondents were price, 21 respondents were Quality, 29 respondents were service and 38 respondents were advertisement.

Table 3.1.6
Respondent Opinion Price of this Brand

Opinion	Total
Highly Satisfied	34
Satisfied	45
Not Satisfied	21
Total	100

Source: Primary Survey 2018

Out of 100 respondents, 34 respondents were purchased the by-products of this brand, 45 respondents were satisfied purchased the by-products of this brand and 21 respondents were not satisfied the by-products of this brand.

Table 3.1.7
Respondents Preferring Arokya Milk

Preferring Arokya	Total
Good flavor	19
Easily available	21
Reasonable price	32
Others	28
Total	100

Source: Primary Survey 2018

Out of 100 respondents, 19 preferred this brand for its good flavor, 21 preferred this brand for its easily available, 32 preferred this brand for its reasonable price and the remaining 28 respondents were not preferred this brand.

Table 3.1.8
Advertisement Drive You Buy To Arokya Milk

Advertisement	Total
Strongly agree	15
Agree	31
No opinion	28
Strongly Disagree	11
Disagree	15
Total	100

Source: Primary Survey 2018

Out of 100 respondents, 15 respondents were strongly agreed, 31 respondents were agree, 28 respondents were given no opinion, 11 respondent was strongly disagreed and 15 respondents were disagreed about advertisement to drive them to buy this brand.

Suggestions and Conclusion

- From this study has been learning to find Arokya milk is highly preferred for its quality. Though some consumers have poor opinion on the price, they prefer mainly for its taste.
- This manuscript has been find Most of consumers have given their voices against sudden increase in the prices.
- This study suggest to advertisement had not created major impact over the consumers. Most of the consumers were unaware about the newly launched advertisements. It would be better if they advertise their brand through leading newspapers and hoardings.
- This paper Arokya milk is not available everywhere, thereby it creates open room to the competitors product like and local brands. Therefore, the sales would become high if it would be sold in every petty shop. So the producer to take necessary step to go behind it as on top of thought this study.
- As above mentioned as ,so it would be much better to sell Arokya milk and its by- products in small and medium sized retail shops.

Conclusion

The study on consumer behavior of Arokya Milk in Coimbatore provided that the most of patrons chosen same features and attributes of the brand. It also attempted to know the different buying conclusion of the consumers. It was also provided an enough data about the satisfaction and an anticipation level of different consumers. The study was also used to understand the different perception of the consumers and how they are loyal to this brand. Thereby, it helped to know the different influencing factors of consumers to prefer the Arokya Milk.

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